

Should All Illicit Drugs be Legalized?

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Abstract

Background: In delving into the intricacies and nuances surrounding the debate of whether or not all illicit drugs should be legalized, the goal was to compare and contrast the research findings of various different economic, medical and sociological studies to determine if the prospective benefits of legalization outweigh the potential cons—with respect to the current systems in North America (Canada and the United States).

Methods: By looking at different data that was collected and interpreted by economists and sociologists as well as incarceration rates and statistics provided by the U.S. Bureau of Justice Statistics database, we can assess the societal costs of drug criminalization and pit this against the potential costs that would be incurred if all drugs were to be legalized. To understand these potential costs we look at the leading causes of drug overdose and addiction in society using collected data from drug overdose toxicology reports as well and crowdfunded survey data and government records. In assessing the different risks posed by certain drugs, we have also taken into consideration the empirical lab studies of medical practitioners and neuroscientists working in the fields of addiction and toxicology.

Results: The research indicates that while insufficient data exists to completely dispel the potential risks associated with the legalization, the evidence to suggest that the criminalization is an effective deterrent from abusing drugs is also insubstantial. The economic merits that would come from the legalization of drugs, through tax and labour income as well as through the reduction of criminal justice costs, are demonstrably significant and feasible to implement.

Conclusions/Interpretation: When compared and contrasted, the research evidenced in these studies suggests that the merits of legalization outweigh the risks associated with doing so.

1. Introduction

The legalization of illicit drugs, whether it's cannabis or opiates, is a contentious subject for understandable reasons. In 2017, exploratory research which collected survey data consisting of 1,013 participants found that 54% knew someone who had died of a drug overdose; 31% of which were close friends, 22.4% were acquaintances, 12.4% were family members, 6.4% were Co-Workers and 1.6% had lost significant others to drug overdoses (AmericanDrugAddictionCenters.org).

The Crack Epidemic of the 1980s and '90s as well as the Opioid/Fentanyl

Crisis, that persists today, demonstrate that the moral and socioeconomic costs of drug addiction are catastrophic. However, determining whether this merits the criminalization of these illicit compounds is less clear. In order to assess this, we must first answer two questions: 1) To what extent is the criminalization of drugs an effective deterrent from using them? and 2) Would legalization lead to more addicts or overdoses in society?

If it is found to be the case that the criminalization of drugs is an effective means of preventing addiction and overdoses, we must then determine if the costs we are currently paying are not

outweighed by the potential benefits that could be yielded through the legalization of drugs.

In addition to the sizeable sales tax revenues that could come about through legalization, other benefits include the potential to end the drug war and the human and monetary costs associated—as well as for those associated with the criminalization of non-violent drug use. The legalizing of illicit drugs could also open the door to the funding of promising new psychiatric treatments involving many different psychotropic compounds which have been marred by the stigma of illegality. Legalization accompanied by various regulatory measures could also lower the rates of overdoses caused by fentanyl tainted drugs sold on the black market.

2. The Potential Costs of Legalization

2.1. Statistical Issues

Proponents of legalization will often cite the moral and financial costs of the mass incarceration of drug-related criminals as a reason for their cause. The common claim that roughly half of all federal inmates (46.7% in 2020) are in for drug-related charges (Carson, 32) is somewhat of a misleading figure when considering that federal inmates (142,028 in 2020)—according to the U.S. Department of Justice (Bureau of Justice Statistics)—accounted for just under 12% of American prisoners in 2020 (Carson, 48-49). Of the roughly 88% of the total U.S. prison population who are incarcerated at the state level (1,040,138 in 2020), in 2019, only

14% were imprisoned for drug-related crimes. Those imprisoned for possession consisted of only 3.8% of state prisoners while the remaining 10.2% were for the selling or trafficking of drugs (Carson, 28).

2.2. The Price of Substance Abuse in Society

Libertarian theorists and proponents of “negative liberty” like the political philosopher Isaiah Berlin would argue that so long as our actions do not impede on others’ ability to live freely—free from fear of violence, frustration and coercion—it is ethically wrong and far too dangerous to allow the state to use its coercive powers to enforce conformity in the hopes of establishing a utopia (Berlin, 118-121). For this reason, it is not the State’s place to stop a non-violent individual from using drugs, should they choose to.

A problem with this take is that it presupposes that it is only the individual who bears the weight of their actions. There has been a societal trend toward treating drug addiction and dependency as a mental illness, one that should be destigmatized and treated the same way we would treat people with depression or post-traumatic stress disorder. In Canada where we have a single-payer medicare system, addiction and mental health services fall into the healthcare budget and in 2017 substance abuse has been estimated to have cost Canadians over \$13.1 billion. This figure does not include measures for lost productivity which were estimated to have amounted to \$20.1 billion or other costs such as motor vehicle collisions and other

accidents where substance use was involved, estimated to cost over \$3.6 billion (Young, Stockwell et al, 2-4).

If presupposed that the legalization of addictive substances like opioids or amphetamines leads to more addictions, it then only adds to the state's financial burden with more mental health service users and prescription methadone addicts. For this reason, drug abuse is inextricably an economic burden on society. Thus the libertarian idea that the state has no moral right to interfere with an individual's actions so long as they are not hurting others, postulated by economists like Milton Friedman, would only hold true if we were to also presume that the government does not assume responsibility for our health—at least not to the degree that it currently does.

The problem with this conclusion is that it assumes that the legalization of illicit drugs would lead to more addiction and overdoses. It also assumes that the punishment can deter drug users and that the criminalization of non-violent drug use is the most effective mechanism we have for preventing people from becoming addicts. While many researchers believe this to be an outdated premise, there are a number who still support it.

A paper published in 2014 by the *New England Journal of Medicine*, examining the adverse health effects of cannabis use concludes that while alcohol and tobacco account for the highest rates of drug-related illnesses, it is not in fact the inherent toxicity of these compounds that makes them more dangerous but rather the legality and socially accepted nature, which make their use so much more prevalent.

The study also concludes that with the legalization of cannabis we can likely expect usage rates to increase as well (Volkow et al, 6-7).

While decriminalization is different from legalization, it is possible that Volkow's conclusion may have been overly hasty when we look at the rates of lifetime drug use of people in Portugal—a country which decriminalized the use and possession of all illicit drugs in July of 2001. Between 2001 and 2007 the number of people who had used any illicit substance in their lifetime had only increased by 4.4%. Use of hashish, a cannabis derivative, increased the most, 4.1%, while the comparatively more dangerous drugs (see table 2 on page 7) barely saw any increase in usage; cocaine 1%, ecstasy 0.6%, amphetamines 0.4% and heroin 0.4% (Hughes et al, 1007). Between 1998 and 2008, the rates of criminal trafficking arrests stayed relatively the same, at a constant rate of about 2,000 people per year, while the overall number of drug-related offences dropped significantly from over 14,000 people in 2000 down to roughly 5,000-5,500 people a year on average, since decriminalization in 2001 (Hughes et al, 1008-1009).

The notion that illicit compounds should be our leading concern, when it comes to addiction and overdose, also becomes problematic when we look at a study from 2012, that used state of North Carolina death records. It was found that—before the rise of fentanyl in 2015 (National Institute on Drug Abuse)—the majority of accidental overdoses could not be attributed to illegal compounds but rather to drugs that were prescribed by a doctor

and taken legally. Prescription opioids were present in 72.2% of autopsy reports while illegal drugs like cocaine and heroin were only present in 16.3% and 22.4% of cases respectively (Austin et al, 44-49). While this could be argued to support Volkow's claims that legal status would increase usage, it is likely imprudent to compare addiction to prescribed pharmacological drugs to recreational cannabis use. The fact that so many are becoming addicted to prescription drugs could perhaps lend itself to the argument that drug addiction is not a choice but a mental illness that should be treated as such.

Table 1: Toxicology results of self-inflicted and unintentional drug overdose deaths in North Carolina in 2012 (Austin et al)

	Self-Inflicted Drug Overdose Decedents N(%) ^c	Unintentional Drug Overdose Decedents N(%) ^c	Chi-Square p-value
Total with toxicology results ^a	158	840	
Substances classified as a contributing cause of death ^b			
Prescription opioids	79 (50.0)	607 (72.2)	< 0.001
Oxycodone	39 (24.7)	246 (29.3)	0.2400
Hydrocodone	21 (12.8)	92 (11.5)	0.3947
Benzodiazepines	158 (38.0)	358 (42.6)	0.2777
Alprazolam	27 (16.4)	251 (31.5)	0.0010
Clonazepam	19 (11.6)	90 (11.2)	0.6279
Antidepressants	71 (45.0)	68 (8.1)	< 0.001
Alcohol	24 (15.2)	117 (13.9)	0.6762
Cocaine	13 (8.2)	137 (16.3)	0.0091
Heroin	1 (0.6)	188 (22.4)	< 0.001

3. The Costs of Not Legalizing

3.1. The Fentanyl Crisis

In recent years the use of synthetic opioids like fentanyl has become the leading cause of lethal overdoses in Canada and the United States. Between 2015 and 2020, the number of deadly overdoses caused by

fentanyl increased by six-times and was found to be present in 69% of all overdoses among males, in the United States in 2020 (National Institute on Drug Abuse).

Due in part to its potency, Fentanyl is an exceedingly cheaper alternative to most illicit substances and it is often used to cut other more expensive drugs like heroin or cocaine, allowing for drug dealers to turn a larger profit. Fentanyl, which is also used as a painkiller by medical professionals, is estimated to be 50-100 times more potent than morphine and thus considerably easier to overdose if not administered correctly (American Addiction Centers).

When we consider that fentanyl was found present in 68% of overdoses by heroin users in 2020 (National Institute on Drug Abuse), it becomes painstakingly obvious that the use of harmful additives in black market drugs is what is causing the increase in accidental deaths—not the illicit drug that was intended to be taken. This also shows why the legalization of drugs may be a superior option to decriminalization. If a regulated and government-sanctioned service—akin to the Société des alcools du Québec (SAQ) for alcohol or the Société québécoise du cannabis (SQDC) for cannabis—were to be instated for all illicit substances, then both addicts and those who choose to use drugs like cocaine recreationally would be able to confidently acquire the substance of their choosing without the risk of unknowingly ingesting something that may be laced with a lethal dose of fentanyl. For this reason, the legalization of all drugs coupled with strict labelling and quality-control regulations

could likely be the solution that saves many lives each year.

3.2. A Missed opportunity for Sales Tax Revenues

The potential for the legalization of drugs to generate government treasury income is considerable when we look at a report from Deloitte Canada. It was estimated that Canada's legalization of cannabis and its derivatives has yielded approximately \$43.5 billion towards Canada's GDP between its legalization date in October of 2018 and October of 2021. \$15.1 billion of which can be attributed directly to government tax revenue and approximately \$25.2 billion in labour income (Diamandiev et al, 6-7). An econometric study from 2017 used crowdsourced data to estimate the price-elasticity of demand of cannabis to help determine the tax revenue potential for the legalized product in the United States. The study used a Full Information Maximum Likelihood (FIML) model to estimate the logarithmic quantity and price of cannabis that would be bought and sold if legalized.

The study determined that at -0.418 cannabis has a similar price elasticity to cigarettes (-0.40) and thus adequately inelastic to assume that the revenue generated would be significant and likely comparable to that of cigarette sales. A similar methodology could be conducted for other illicit drugs and then pooled to determine the substantiality of the potential excise tax revenues—were all drugs to be legalized (Halcoussis et al, 131-132).

The same FIML model could be altered to predict the earnings potential for other illicit substances. The model used by Halcoussis et al is given below with various alterations to show how it could be reapplied for other drugs and countries, like cocaine in a Canadian market (Halcoussis et al, 126-127).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ln}(Q_i) = & B_0 + B_1. \text{Ln}(P_i) + B_2. \\ & \text{QUALITY}_{1i} + B_3. \text{QUALITY}_{3i} + B_4. \\ & \text{Ln}(\text{INCOME}_i) + B_5. \text{ARRESTS}_i + B_6. \\ & \text{Ln}(\text{DISTANCE}_i) + e_i \end{aligned}$$

$\text{Ln}(Q_i)$ = the natural log of the cannabis quantity, in grams, could be altered to a smaller metric like milligrams for a drug like cocaine which is typically sold and consumed in much smaller quantities than cannabis.

$\text{Ln}(P_i)$ = the natural log of cannabis price in USD, per gram, could be altered to price in CAD per milligram of cocaine.

$\text{QUALITY}_{1i} = 1$ if the quality of the drug in question is “low”—out of a categorical scale of low, medium or high quality. QUALITY_{1i} will be equal to 0 otherwise. The study used priceofweed.com to gather the consumer's quality ratings. A similar approach could likely be used for other drugs like cocaine.

$\text{QUALITY}_{3i} = 1$ if the quality of the drug is high— QUALITY_{3i} will otherwise be equal to 0. Data would be

gathered the same way as for QUALITY_i.

Ln(INCOME_i) = the natural log of yearly median household income (in thousands USD). This could easily be changed to fit a Canadian demographic using median household income data, readily available from Statistics Canada.

ARRESTS_i = the number of arrests, per 100 000 Canadians, related to the drug in question (possession or selling).

Ln(DISTANCE_i) = the natural log of the average number of miles between the location where the transaction took place and the major production regions for the drug in question. The study looked at average distances between the U.S. counties where transactions occurred and several states in Mexico which are considered the major hotspots for cannabis production, later consumed in the U.S.

One problem with this method is in the fact that marijuana is not heroin and—as seen in table 2—poses a considerably lower risk of dependency or death than the latter—thus neglecting the negative externalities that may potentially come with legalizing substances harder than cannabis.

3.3. A Missed Opportunity for New Treatment Methods

It is intellectually dishonest to lump all illicit drugs into the same category. The effects of different drugs vary radically from one another and some are vastly more harmful than others. There is also remarkably little correlation between the legality of a substance and its purported risks—both in terms of lethality and addictiveness—as seen in table 2. (Gable, 149).

Table 2: Safety Ratio and Dependence Potential of Psychoactive Drugs (Gable, 149)

Substance	Effective Dose	Lethal Dose	Safety Ratio	Dependence Potential
<i>Narcotics</i>				
Heroin (iv) ²	8 mg	50 mg	6	Very high
Morphine (or)	20 mg	300 mg	15	High
<i>Depressants (sedative hypnotics)</i>				
<i>Barbiturates</i>				
Pentobarbital (or)	250 mg	5 g	20	Moderate/high
<i>Benzodiazepines</i>				
Rohypnol (or)	1 mg	30 mg	30	Moderate
<i>Alcohol</i>				
Ethanol (or)	30 mg ³	300 mg	10	Moderate
<i>Stimulants</i>				
Caffeine (or)	100 mg ⁴	10 g	100	Moderate/low
Cocaine (in)	80 mg ⁵	1.2 g	15	Moderate/high
Ephedra (or)	25 mg	3.5 g ⁶	140	Moderate
MDMA (or)	125 mg	2 g	16	Moderate/low
Nicotine (sm)	1 mg ⁷	50 mg	50	High
<i>Anesthetics</i>				
Ketamine (in)	70 mg	2.7 g (?)	38 (?)	Low
Nitrous oxide (inh)	3.5 liters	525 liters ⁸	150	Moderate/low
<i>Hallucinogens</i>				
LSD (or)	100 mcg	100 mg	1000	Very low
Mescaline (or)	350 mg	8.4 g (?)	24 (?)	Very low
Psilocybin (or)	6 mg	6 g (?)	1000 (?)	Very low
<i>Cannabis</i>				
Marijuana (sm)	15 mg	> 15 g	>1000	Moderate/low

¹ Adapted in part from Gable (2004a,b). The information presented here should not be used as a dosage guide. Significant differences exist with respect to a person's physiological and psychological reactions. The dosage indicated is the estimated median quantity for a 70kg adult human who has not developed tolerance to the substance.

² Routes of administration: in = intranasal (insufflation/snorting); inh = inhaled, iv = intravenous, or = oral, sm = smoked.

³ Approximately two 12-ounce beers or malt liquor at 5.5 percent by volume, or equivalent ethanol in other alcohol drinks.

⁴ Approximately 1.5 cups of 148 ml (5 oz.) of fluid coffee per cup.

⁵ Assumes three "lines" containing between 20 and 30 mg cocaine each.

⁶ Lethal dose not clearly established; estimate based on nonhuman animal studies.

⁷ Approximately one cigarette.

⁸ Nitrous oxide—when used with sufficient oxygen—has not been demonstrated to be lethal.

(Acute toxicity of drugs versus regulatory status)

There is also an important distinction to be made between drugs that are scientifically determined to be non-habit-forming and those which are. Psychedelic drugs like psilocybin

mushrooms and lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD or “acid”) have been found by neuroscientists to operate outside of dopamine pathways in the brain and there is currently no hard evidence that they are intrinsically habit-forming in the way that drugs like methamphetamine or crack cocaine are (Nichols, 272).

In recent years more research has been done on the potential therapeutic applications of many illegal drugs that have been marred by an association with recreational use. These are studies, which could have led to the development of new treatment methods that could have helped millions of people but may have long gone unfunded due to the illegality of the compounds in question and the stigma associated with them (Nichols, 329).

For instance, promising research has been conducted by psychiatrists demonstrating that psychedelic drugs like N,N-Dimethyltryptamine (DMT), psilocybin mushrooms and LSD could be effectively used to combat addiction. Studies led by the Canadian psychiatrists Osmond and Hoffer found promising evidence that LSD could be used in the treatment of those struggling with alcoholism. In a review of multiple studies carried out between 1953-69, containing over 1100 patients who had been treated for alcoholism with LSD. Approximately 75% of these patients had seen an improvement after 10 months, compared to only 44% for the control group. (Nichols, 329)

Methylenedioxymethamphetamine (MDMA or “ecstasy”) has been found in clinical trials to have promising effects for those suffering from

post-traumatic-stress-disorder (PTSD). A placebo-controlled study conducted in 2011 by Mithoefer et al. looked at the use of MDMA administered in concurrence with psychotherapy to a test-group of twenty individuals suffering from chronic PTSD. Results showed significant discrepancies between those who were administered the MDMA and the placebo group, with ten out of the twelve (83%) showing a significant enough decrease in the severity of their symptoms to no longer qualify as suffering under the DSM-IV standards, compared to only two out of the eight (25%) participants who were given placebos (Nichols, 332).

While these are factors worth considering, it should be noted that these treatments have only been approved for clinical trials and data is relatively limited therefore we are currently unable to determine on a societal scale what the statistical effects on nationwide drug addiction and recovery rates would be.

3.4. The Current Costs of the Drug War

The price of criminalizing drugs is indisputably high. In Canada alone, the criminal justice costs of fighting substance abuse were estimated at \$9.2 billion in 2017 (Young, Stockwell et al, 2-4). When considering the human costs of the Mexican Cartel Wars, however, we see that the war on drugs is as much a moral crisis as it is an economic one.

Drug-related homicides have cost the lives of roughly 150,000 Mexicans since 2006, and this figure does not include the roughly 73,000 people who are missing and presumed to have been killed by the cartels

(Congressional Research Service, 6). The problem extends beyond Mexico's borders and Canadians and Americans are complicit since the vast majority of hard drugs, including cocaine, heroin and methamphetamine, consumed in Canada and the United States were ultimately trafficked from South and Central America, either directly or indirectly through the cartels and their affiliates. (Congressional Research Service, 13-14)

Drugs like cannabis, which are relatively easy to grow, only yielded their street price tag because of their illegality—the condition that made these drugs relatively scarce. This has been seen in states like California where legalization, allowing for anyone to grow the substance, has thereby decreased the profitability of the black market trade. One study found that cannabis users in California view the legal product as a superior commodity to its illegal counterpart and thus are even willing to pay a higher premium for it, with an asymmetric substitution equivalency of roughly \$15 a gram for the legal and \$10 for illegal product. The study concluded that so long as the price for legal cannabis does not significantly exceed this substitution rate, legalization does not increase the demand for illegal cannabis and may actually disincentivize the illegal market for it (Amlung et al, 116-117).

Since there is no reason to believe that this would not be the case for other illicit drugs, this research suggests that absolute legalization could be the best strategy we have for fighting the ongoing drug war and preventing further violence

propagated by the cartels and their associates.

4. Summary and Conclusions

Evidenced in the research, the potential socio-economic benefits of legalizing all currently illicit drugs are considerably large. The successful track record for cannabis legalization suggests that the national wealth that could be generated through both labour income and excise taxes is both feasible and significant. There is also ample evidence to suggest that legalization would come with a number of positive externalities. In addition to decreasing the criminal justice and law-enforcement costs associated with the ongoing war on drugs, legalization could also disincentivize the illegal market for these substances, greatly reducing the rates of drug cartel-related violence. Legalization could also help in preventing overdose deaths caused by the use of additives like fentanyl which are increasingly prevalent in the illegal products.

While there is currently not enough data to completely dismiss the concerns of increased usage rates, were all drugs to be legalized, the evidence to support the efficacy of criminal punishment in deterring drug use is also markedly insubstantial. For this reason, it seems likely that the merits of legalization outweigh the potential cons.

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